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ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF DISTANCE LEARNING

Annotation. Distance learning will inevitably force you to fight the most severe opponent — your own laziness. And if you are not ready for this fight, it is better not to start the fight at all. However, if you are confident in your abilities and are determined to learn, distance education will offer you a variety of opportunities for professional and personal improvement. Distance learning has developed over years from satellite video courses to modern videoconferencing through personal computers.

The article is devoted to the study of the psychological and organizational features of distance learning in the modern conditions of the development of education at the university. The psychological characteristics of students, their difficulties during training are determined. The problems faced by teachers in the organization and implementation of distance learning are also clarified.

Key words: higher education, higher school, educational process, self-education, psychological and pedagogical features, personality, student, teacher, distance learning.

Distance education allows students in modern social and economic conditions to become a well-educated person who can flexibly adjust the content of their activities according to the requirements of rapidly developing dentistry. Students studying in the distance education system are mainly engaged in professional self-development at a convenient time for them. So, distance education can be considered as a space of self-actualization of the individual. Distance learning is fundamentally different from traditional forms of learning. One of the modern requirements

for the education system is attention to the individuality of the student. The use of computer technologies in distance education of students, allows to improve its cognitive processes. The introduction of distance education fundamentally changes the role positions of “teacher-student”. In the traditional form of teaching, the teacher acts as an interpreter of knowledge. With the expansion of the educational space, the function of interpreting knowledge is assumed by the student, and the teacher is the coordinator of this knowledge. He advises students, directs the work of the cognitive processes of the student, that is, takes on the functions of supporting the professional development of the student [1 p. 50-53]. Almost all developed countries consider the development of distance education a priority and annually allocate considerable funds for these programs. Naturally, the United States is ahead of the rest of the planet. Probably, because in this country all the best has come together for the development of this type of education. Some experts in this field predict the further dominance of distance education over traditional forms of education and the complete displacement of the latter in the future. But, probably, this will not happen, just as it happened with the replacement of theaters with the film industry, television, etc. The popularity of distance education is growing, as it has many advantages. First-mass character. The number of people studying in the same programs at the same university is determined only by the characteristics of the communication equipment. By the way, it was the mass nature and accessibility that became the motivation for the emergence of distance education. The second advantage of distance education is “speed”. The third is the relative cheapness of obtaining knowledge. On average, getting a degree from a western university will cost you about ten times less.

However, there are still quite a few educational institutions that offer distance education in its purest form and in all specialties. But it is all coming to this. So, in general, the main differences and advantages of distance learning from traditional forms of learning are: - the opportunity to study at a convenient time, in a convenient place and pace. Non-regulated period of time for the development of the discipline; - parallel training with professional activities, i.e. on-the-job training; - concentrated imagination of educational information and multi-access to it increases the efficiency of material assimilation; - the use of the latest achievements of information and telecommunications technologies in the educational process teaches and works with them; - equal opportunities for education regardless of the place of residence, health status, elitism and material security of the student; - export and import of world achievements in the market of educational services; - distance learning expands and updates the role of the teacher, who must coordinate the cognitive process, constantly improve the courses taught by him, increase creative activity and qualifications in accordance with innovations and innovations; - distance education also has a positive impact on the student, increasing his creative and intellectual potential through self-organization, the desire for knowledge, the ability to interact with computer technology and make responsible decisions independently.

In the complex of psychological features of distance learning, there are several groups that require special attention. First, this is the definition of the age range of students capable of distance learning and the description of the psychological characteristics of these students [2, p. 30-32]. In our opinion, the currently available forms of distance learning are most suitable for adults receiving additional education or undergoing retraining, but with a certain refinement of working programs on the content of training, considering modern requirements, it is also possible to train university students, as evidenced by the results of our study. The formation of the integrity of the intellect is a long-term and contradictory process. Ananyev noted that the leading role in this process is played by education (the amount of knowledge acquired, the general level of information) and training (activities for the assimilation of knowledge, skills, and abilities). As a result of the comprehensive research conducted, B. G. Ananyev came to an important conclusion: during adult development, the degree of knowledge acquisition increases. In foreign psychology, the problem of interrupting traditional distance learning is recognized by all and is being studied quite actively. Satisfaction with communication with the teacher was the most influential factor in the students’ decision to continue or terminate distance learning. In a study by Cascelli, Deneher, and Prunell, it

was found that contact with a teacher is necessary for students not only to clarify obscure learning topics, but also to maintain motivation to learn and collaborate with fellow students. Thus, not only insufficient communication with the teacher affects the appearance of the desire to interrupt distance learning, but also limited communication with fellow students is essential. In a study by G. Astleitner and A. Sindler conducted in 1999, it was revealed that, even though all students were satisfied with the content of the distance course, they considered the main disadvantages of distance learning to be the lack of emotional contacts with classmates and the inability to discuss emotional problems. For example, research conducted at the British Open University allowed us to determine the requirements for students and teachers: polite, respectful treatment; transparent and objective system of grades and degrees; explanations and justifications of the assessment of the acquired knowledge; students' understanding of the significance of the assessments. According to the results of the conducted research, some Western researchers have tried to suggest certain mechanisms for solving this problem. J. Keller in 1997 proposed to rebuild the learning process based on the ARCS — Attention — Relevance — Confidence — Satisfaction model (attention, significance, confidence, satisfaction). L. Visser used a simplified version of the ARSC model, focusing not on the restructuring of the teaching process, but on changing the motivation of distance learners. She developed a program of “motivational messages” that were sent to students. As a result of this experiment, the learning process significantly improved and received a better emotional assessment [3, p. 7-12]. Of course, we need to consider the experience of Western and American scientists. But, in the course of the study, we identified the difficulties that teachers face at our university when implementing distance courses or distance learning systems. They should include the need for course authors to independently structure the training material, inevitably adapting it to the requirements of a personal computer. For many (especially humanitarians), this process is not obvious and is very painful. Conservatism of the teaching staff is an equally difficult organizational problem, which can lead to fatal consequences for the introduction of a distance learning system within an educational institution. The rapid renewal of technical capabilities for organizing self-education is extremely relevant to the problem of the transition from sporadic, and sometimes chaotic, use of the latest technical and information tools (especially the Internet) to a normalized, structurally well-built, and purposeful [2, p. 33].

Conclusions. We have determined that distance learning students have difficulties in establishing contact. They reliably evaluate teachers worse on personal and professional qualities. The “I” image is characterized by a less positive attitude towards oneself than during traditional university studies. So, distance learning students pointed out the presence of such educational problems: 1) the need for obtaining and consolidating knowledge in the specialty is not met; the need for a better test of knowledge, a lack of evaluation in the learning process. Lack of communication with the teacher. Students realize that the teacher is the most important translator of experience, without which professional socialization is impossible; 2) the lack of creative self-realization of students in the process of distance learning. So, according to the results of the study, we concluded that the formal approach to the organization and implementation of the educational process in the distance learning system takes place in the “zone of actual development”, which is unjustifiably easy for students and loses its developing effect. The creators of the “cases” are not significant people for students who are in the distance learning system.

The main reason for the dissatisfaction of the individual with the distance learning system is the lack of communication with the teacher. The person of the distance learning form has difficulties in establishing contact in the context of the educational system; reliably evaluates teachers worse on personal and professional qualities; cares little about his future profession, as if he “does not see” himself in it. There are no clearly expressed problems in the communication of distance learning students. The level of subjective control (internal personal responsibility) of distance learning students does not differ from students of the traditional form of education at

the university. So, the main psychological problem of distance learning today is communication or emotional interaction between the teacher and students, as well as between the students themselves. The development and implementation of various mechanisms to compensate for social and emotional dissatisfaction with the process of interaction in the teacher-student and student-student system can significantly increase the effectiveness of distance learning. This can be facilitated by the introduction of programs that allow for live interactive communication between the teacher and the student. Unfortunately, not everything can be studied remotely. In some cases, you cannot do without practical training under the guidance of an experienced mentor. You can study history or literature remotely, or you can become an excellent designer or programmer. But you cannot train to be a pilot or a surgeon.

Perhaps, soon, the situation will change. One day, virtual reality technology will allow people from all over the world to participate in joint laboratory work. When this happens, the list of professions and skills that can be learned remotely will greatly expand.

Lack of personal communication. Full-time training is valuable not only for a set of knowledge. An important element of offline learning is personal communication. After receiving a traditional higher education, the student spends several years stewing in the boiling cauldron of university life. He interacts with teachers and classmates in an informal setting. Such communication can generate amazing ideas and radically change the fate of people. If Bill Gates had been educated remotely at Harvard, he would never have met Steve Ballmer and founded Microsoft.

The absence of positive “side effects”. The fact that distance learning gives a person a specific set of knowledge can be considered not only a plus, but also a minus. Studying remotely, a person deprives himself of many positive “side effects” of academic education.

For example, the process of taking notes of long lectures trains the speed of writing, develops mechanical memory, and teaches you to isolate the most important fragments from the flow of information on the go. All these skills are very useful in everyday life, but distance learning does not give them.

In the process of distance learning, you will probably encounter unforeseen circumstances that will hinder you. For example, at the most inopportune moment, you can turn off the light or the computer fails. And the Internet can be cut off right during an important online seminar, and there is nothing you can do about it. Remote learning makes you dependent on technical means.

Of course, on the way to the university, you can get stuck in the elevator. But if you have already reached the physical place of study, there is little that can prevent you from gaining knowledge.

The lack of constant supervision on the part of the teacher is a minus, which can easily be confused with a plus. But it is not that simple. At first, the student may feel that the lack of control gives him additional freedom. In fact, distance learning requires a strong motivation and strict self-discipline from the student. Thus, distance learning is a dynamically developing form of education today. This form, of course, has a place to be in modern society, but, despite all the obvious advantages, it still needs to be improved.

List of literature:

1 www.dis-edu.ru.

2 www.istu.edu.

3 Gozman L.Y, Shestopal E.B “Distance education at the threshold of the XXI century” - Rostov - on - Don, 1999.-131 p.

4 Clarine M. “Innovations in education. Metaphors and models” - M.: Nauka, 1997.- 109 p.